

A FLEXED HAND POSTURE TO PREVENT PRIMITIVE RAYNAUD'S PHENOMENON'S SYMPTOMS

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ABSTRACT

Starting from mathematical arguments, we contend that biomechanical changes in hand grasping may affect the fingers' physiopathology. During hand prehension, the fingers are brought together so that a pen can be picked up or a roll of scotch tape can be enveloped. The very contact between the fingers produces transient topological changes that turn the homogeneous three-dimensional hand into a donut-like torus. We argue that the occurrence of a hole bordered by grasping fingers has implications for the primitive Raynaud's phenomenon (henceforward RP), a common disease characterized by cold-related peripheral blood-flow restriction. We suggest a prophylactic hand posture in daily living to prevent RP's symptoms and relapses, characterized by all the fingers flexed to touch the palm as long as possible. The contact between the fingers and the palm creates a topological hole that modifies the natural thermal and electric gradients on the skin surface. When the heat is transferred along the toroidal geodesic lines from the palm to the closed fingers, the benefits for RP patients are such as uniform increase in fingers temperature, improved blood microcirculation, inflammation decline and wound healing. Our simple, topologically-framed behavioral approach to RP patients might contribute to improve their quality of life, allowing them to resume their active preinjury lifestyle.

Keywords: topological distance; flow; hand biomechanics; grip; capillary drainage.

INTRODUCTION

The Raynaud's phenomenon (henceforward RP) is a common vasospastic condition characterized by transient and peripheral blood-flow restriction, usually related with cold environments and periods of emotional stress. Caused by vasoconstriction of the digital arteries and cutaneous arterioles, RP can be categorized as either primary, or secondary, the latter being associated with a wide range of etiologies (Brorsson et al., 2012; Landim et al. 2019; Teaw et al., 2023). The primitive RP affects approximately 5% of the general population (Haque 2020) and may lead to significant discomfort and impaired quality of life (Su et al., 2021). Compared with healthy controls, RP patients display lower hands' temperature pre and post cold test, decreased blood flow on radial artery, impaired lateral pinch strength, decreased ranges of motions at passive extension of forefinger and active flexion/extension of thumb (Tapia-Haro et al., 2023; Brunner-Ziegler et al., 2024).

Starting with mathematical arguments from the branch of topology, we argue that dynamical changes in hand grasping may affect the physiopathology of the fingers. This leads us to suggest a simple prophylactic hand posture that might contribute to improve the quality of life of the patients affected by primary RP.

TOPOLOGY OF HAND PREHENSION

The hand is made up of a stable wrist with at least two digits that can oppose against each other with the appropriate power, making contact with the object's surface (Brand and Hollister, 1999; Tanrikulu et al., 2015; Jaworski and Karpiński, 2017; Schreuders et al. 2019). The terms hand grasp, grip and prehension are interchangeable (Chen et al., 2020; Hartmann et al., 2023). Different classifications label the few basic functions making up most hand movements (see, e.g., Schlesinger 1919; Smith et al., 1995; Hertling and Kessler, 1996; Duncan et al., 2013):

- 1) The precision pinch, otherwise known as terminal grasp, palmar grasp, pulp to pulp, tip-to tip pinch. The fingernail tips are brought together so that a small item, such as a pen, can be picked up and manipulated with great precision (**Figure 1A**).
- 2) The oppositional pinch, otherwise known as the subterminal or lateral grasp, allows for increased forces to be generated through lateral thumb opposition. This grasp occurs, e.g., when one holds a ticket (**Figure 1B**).
- 3) The key pinch maneuvering requires a stable post provided by the index finger. This grasp is used when holding a key (**Figure 1C**).

- 4) The chuck grip, otherwise known as the directional grip or cylindrical grasp, is used to envelop small diameter cylindrical objects (**Figure 1D**).
- 5) The hook grip is used when a suitcase or a briefcase is picked up (**Figure 1E**).
- 6) The span grasp maneuver or spherical grasp is used to grab a ball (**Figure 1F**).
- 7) The power grasp position is used for movements like gripping a club or a bat (**Figure 1G**).

We focus here on the precision pinch and the hook grip (henceforward grasps 1 and 5) since they can be envisaged as examples of topological holes in biophysical systems. Two objects are called topologically different if they differ in the number of their holes (Tozzi et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2020). For instance, a sphere, a triangle or a square do not contain holes and are said to have genus 0, a donut contains a hole and has genus 1, while the number 8 contains two holes and has genus 2. When the grasps 1 and 5 occur, a three-dimensional object of genus zero becomes a donut-like torus of genus one (**Figures 1H-L**).

We will show in the sequel that, once the hand's topological homogeneity is temporarily broken by the very occurrence of the hole enclosed by the fingers, unexpected biomechanical, biophysical and pathological implications are spawned.

Figure 1. Topology of hand grasping. **Figures A-G.** Basic types of prehension as defined by Schlesinger (1919), Smith et al. (1995); Duncan et al. (2013). See the text for the nomenclature and further details.

Figures H-L. Topological modifications during hand grasping. A human hand before (**Figure H**) and after a precision pinch (**Figure I**) and after a hook grip (**Figure L**). Before the grips, the hand is a topological object of genus zero. After the grips, a hole is formed and the hand turns into a topological object of genus one, namely, a donut-like torus.

Geodetics on genus one manifolds. A genus zero object can be topologically described as a continuous three-dimensional manifold, while a genus one object can be described as a donut-like torus. The flows taking place on the surface of the two objects are quite different. Unlike the case of the three-dimensional planar geometry, the non-uniform toroidal curvature requires a distinct spectrum of eigenfrequencies and basis functions to propagate waves (Busuioc et al., 2019). A toroidal path can be described in terms of a geodetic line, i.e., the shortest distance between two points on the surface of the solid (Le Brigant and Preston, 2023). The geodetics can be either a series of annuli running around the circumference, or a series of straight lines parallel to the axis, or a series of spiral, helicoid curves winding round the wall of the torus (Jantzen 2012; Celarno et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023). Geodetics may be constrained to go twice or many times round the surface, self-intersecting or not self-intersecting (d’Arcy Wentworth Thompson, 1942). They may cross any point on the donut-like surface, converging and diverging from the meridians, looping around the torus, crossing or matching the inner and outer equators. **Figure 2** illustrates a few examples of toroidal geodetics.

In the cases of the grasps 1 and 5, when a torus is temporarily produced by the very contact between the fingers, transient biophysical flows are generated that must follow geodetic paths on the toroidal hand surface. In the sequel, we will show that these newly generated geodetic flows have unnoticed implications for RP patients.

Figure 2. Different paths of geodetics moving across the surface of a torus. **Figures A-C.** Torus paths are curves on the toroidal surface that can wind many times, producing circles around and through the hole. Modified from Verhoeff (2011). **Figure D.** Two sets of geodesics emanating from a “base point” are plotted for a length given by the radius (thin curves). The two sets focus along curves called conjugate loci, whose components are shown as either heavy red or heavy blue curves. Modified from Cherrie and Waters (2016).

PHYSIOLOGICAL OUTCOMES OF DONUT-LIKE HAND PREHENSION

We stated that, during the grasps 1 and 5, biophysical flows are generated, mostly occurring along the geodetics of the torus. The grasps 1 and 5 produce a thermal gradient impacting the fingers’ blood microcirculation. Laboratory experiments suggest that raises in temperature enhance capillary flow performance and increase capillary pressure hysteresis between drainage and imbibition (Biswas and Kartha 2019; Fang et al., 2020; Standnes and Fotland, 2021). Concerning the skin, it has been demonstrated that reduction in cutaneous temperature decreases capillary red cell velocity, capillary flow and hyperemia duration (Szilágyi, et al., 1971; Hales et al., 1978; Klabunde and Johnson, 1980; Ye and Griffin, 2011). The capillary pressure at the base of the fingers’ nails increases when skin temperature is heightened over physiological ranges, generating hand vasodilation to enhance heat dissipation (Levick and Michel, 1978; Hirata 2017). Since the capillary pressure in the warm hand is never less than the plasma colloid osmotic pressure, fluid cannot be reabsorbed from the tissues into the capillaries (Levick and Michel, 1978). It is noteworthy that the relative change in capillary pressure with temperature is not equal to that of the surface tension of water, but rather it is roughly

four times as large (Grant and Bachmann, 2002). This means that a seemingly insignificant phenomenon like the thumb touching the forefinger has important consequences on capillary pressure.

The bodily temperature also influences the immune system by acting on the expression of leukocyte surface antigens (Jämsä et al., 2011) and on leukocyte recruitment, i.e., the immunological process enabling the extravasation of circulating leukocytes into tissues (Köllner and Kotterba, 2002; Kurz et al., 2018). In-vitro models suggest that continued hypothermia significantly inhibits transendothelial migration of leukocytes, whereas rewarming process strongly enhances transmigration (Bogert et al., 2016). The exercise and the ensuing thermal increases lead to leukocyte mobilization and cytokine production (Peake et al., 2008; Shutova and Boehncke, 2022). Blood vessels' delayed flow regulation due to temperature decreases may contribute to pathological conditions, like the microvascular disease in diabetes mellitus (Wang et al., 2021).

During grasps 1 and 5, the heat is transferred between the fingers, generating a thermal gradient running along the toroidal geodetics. The ensuing increases in fingers temperature contribute to enhance blood flow, causing inflammation decline and wound healing. This leads us to RF, whose incidence is notably higher in colder climates. The key to managing primary RF lies in maintaining warmth in affected extremities to prevent symptom flare-ups (Landim et al. 2019). Different approaches have been used to keep the extremities warm and to boost blood circulation, including the use of specialized gloves and mittens, electronic hand warmers, grip hand exercisers, skin moisturizing, cold avoidance habits, keep hands moving (Ture et al., 2024). We suggest here a new type of prophylactic approach. To prevent the cold-induced RP symptoms, we suggest to train the patients to keep as much as possible the hands in a flexed posture where the fingers continuously touch the palm of the hand (**Figure 3**).

In sum, the transient formation of a toroidal structure during hand prehension could lead to local increases in fingers temperature and circulation, providing endothelial protection in RP patients at risk of ischemic injury. We suggest that a prophylactic hand stance in daily living can be used to retain warmth and promote blood circulation in the extremities.

Figure 3A. Prophylactic hand posture to prevent Raynaud phenomenon's symptoms and relapses. **Figure 3B** illustrates some of the beneficial thermal flows taking place along the donut-like structure formed by the prophylactic hand posture.

CONCLUSIONS

Topological approaches provide tools for measuring the large-scale properties of spaces and metrics, ignoring the objects' small-scale details and parameters like stiffness, viscosity, etc. Topology concerns not just mathematical shapes, but also physical features such as signals, energies, temperatures, densities, etc. For a survey, see Tozzi et al., 2017. Looking for topological features in biophysical settings, we opted for hand grasping as a paradigmatic example of the topological occurrence of holes in biophysical systems, since the hand is easily available to investigators via noninvasive, fast, economical, standardized and reproducible methods. Starting from this purely mathematical approach, we proposed a prophylactic hand posture in daily living that could help patients affected by primitive RP to resume their active preinjury lifestyle and employment. The prophylactic hand stance suggested by us can be achieved without force exertions and constraints since it bears strong resemblance to the finger's natural posture, characterized by a slight joints' flexion (Li and Yue, 2002; Lee et al., 2008; Lee and Jung, 2014; Romano et al., 2019).

Apart from the beneficial thermal gradients, healthy epidermis actively generates small electric currents playing roles in cell communication, skin integrity and wound healing (Abe and Nishizawa, 2021). The injured skin produces significant wound currents that are essential for the healing process, as they guide the repair cells' division and migration to the wound site (Reid and Zhao, 2014). The skin's resistance increases with distance from the surface and varies widely among individuals and across different body areas, with the lowest resistance found on the palms and soles due to the higher moisture and sweat gland activity (Kolimechkov et al., 2023). During the grasps 1 and 5, a process occurs analogous to the closure of an electrical circuit and an electric gradient is generated. This means that the cutaneous currents are free to propagate throughout the donut-like fingers, with beneficial effects in wound healing and integrity preservation. It is noteworthy that the skin's electrical properties can be also altered by the above mentioned thermal changes, since higher temperatures increase skin permeability and reduce resistance. It is mandatory to acknowledge the need for additional empirical validation to our exploration of the topological aspects of hand grasping. The integration of computational models and experimental data could strengthen the argument and provide a clearer understanding of the practical significance of the observed topological features in real-world physiological contexts.

DECLARATIONS

Ethics approval and consent to participate: This research does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by the Authors.

Consent for publication: The Authors transfer all copyright ownership, in the event the work is published. The undersigned authors warrant that the article is original, does not infringe on any copyright or other proprietary right of any third part, is not under consideration by another journal, and has not been previously published.

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